

The Physical and Mechanical Properties of Coral Sand

Md Mahmudul Hasan , Md Bourhan Kabir , Md Safiq Raihan Prodhan ,
Md Shahjahan Anik , Ahamed Zubaer , Md Rajib Hasan , Md Nasrullah Sami
Shandong University of Technology, China

Suggested Citation

Hasan, M.M., Kabir, M.B.,
Prodhan, M.S.R., Anik, M.S.
Zubaer, A., Hasan, M.R. & Sami,
M.N. (2024). The Physical and
Mechanical Properties of Coral
Sand. *European Journal of Theoretical
and Applied Sciences*, 2(1), 313-337.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(1\).27](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(1).27)

Abstract:

Coral sand interacts with a variety of particles and species in tropical marine habitats due to its special characteristics. Particular emphasizes the benefits of using contemporary mathematical technologies to examine the characteristics and behavior of coral sand for engineering applications. Coral sand's composition and creation processes influence its distinctive qualities. Coral sand is mostly made up of the skeletal remains of tiny coral polyps and has a white or off-white appearance due to its high calcium carbonate content. Particularly in the area of geotechnical engineering, the interaction of coral sand particles is of great importance. Particle

form, size distribution, and interparticle forces are a few examples of the variables that affect how coral sand behaves as a granular material. Investigations on its geotechnical characteristics, such as its shear strength, permeability, and compressibility, are the main focus of current research. To learn more about the engineering behavior of coral sand, researchers are examining field monitoring approaches and laboratory testing procedures. Additionally, research aims to comprehend how biological activity, cementation, and particle form affect coral sand's mechanical characteristics. In the coral sand study, the benefit of contemporary computation technologies is remarkable. Advanced computer methods, in combination with numerical modeling and simulation approaches, provide precise forecasting of coral sand behavior under various loading and climatic conditions. Engineers may use these technologies to examine foundation design issues, determine the stability of coastal buildings, and create methods for controlling coastal erosion. The study of coral sand and its characteristics has important ramifications for geotechnical engineering. The capacity to assess and construct engineering structures in coral sand settings is improved by the application of contemporary computation technologies.

Keywords: *Characteristics coral sand, Interaction particles, Calculation technology, Durability of foundation.*

Introduction

The sedimentary particles that make up sandy shorelines and shallow marine habitats in tropical areas are referred to as coral sand. The majority of its material is made up of the skeletal fragments of coral creatures, which are microscopic polyps of the Anthozoa type of marine life. Coral polyps create their exoskeletons by removing calcium carbonate

from the surrounding saltwater, gradually constructing intricate structures known as coral reefs. Natural occurrences, including wave motion and attrition, cause the skeletons of these coral creatures to fracture when they die. These particles help create coral sand together with other biological and inorganic components.

In accordance with the particular coral species that are local to the location, the nature of coral

reef sand might change. It often has a white or off-white tint because of the calcium carbonate that makes up most of it. Other elements, such as minerals and biological materials, such as shells from sea algae and shell pieces, may also be present in the sand, giving it different hues and textures.

Coral reef sand is an essential component of tropical marine ecology. Little vertebrates, young fish, and other marine animals may all find homes there. The complex structure of coral sand aids in nutrient cycling and water filtration, enhancing the overall health of coral reef ecosystems. From a geological standpoint, coral sand has been essential to the development and maintenance of coral reefs. These reefs have the potential to expand and evolve into vast and diversified ecosystems, sustaining a variety of marine species throughout time as coral sand and other sedimentary materials accumulate. However, it is crucial to remember that human activity and environmental changes may severely threaten coral reefs and the coral sand that is linked to them. Climate change, pollution, overfishing, and damaging fishing methods are just a few of the factors that may have a disastrous impact on coral reefs and lead to the depletion of coral sand resources. Coral sand is a kind of sediment that is mostly found in tropical and subtropical regions (i.e., 30°N and 30°S) and is produced by the bioerosion of the limestone that makes up the skeletons of marine animals.

In recent years, extensive studies have been performed to understand the differences in engineering properties between coral sand and silica sand (Lyu et al 2019; Peng et al 2021; Shen et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021a; 2019b; Wu et al., 1994; Yu et al., 2019) found that coral sand with rough surface and interior have unique tree-shaped and rod-shaped particles and have typical co-cave hole characteristic.

Compared with that of silica sand, the particle shape of coral sand is more irregular, and the inter-granular pores are larger under the same accumulation conditions (Wang et al, 2022).

Yu et al. (2019) studied the attenuation effects of stress wave in granular media and found coral

sand has a greater wave attenuation effect than the silica sand. The sole material that allows coral reefs to develop is coral sand. It is created as a result of the erosive action, movement, and accumulation of coral, shell, algae, and other biological detritus across the water. The skeleton-formed particles had internal pores and live passages that the corals left behind. Coral sand is the only material that can transport freshwater lenses on many man-made and biological islands and reefs in the Sansha region of China. Consequently, in order to understand the processes that lead to the development and growth of freshwater lenses, it is important to look into the water-physical characteristics of coral sand. Since the time horizon for freshwater lens research is often many years to several decades, numerical modeling has emerged as a popular technique. Having precise hydrogeological parameters and stratigraphic data for the island and reef development is one of the crucial requirements for the numerical simulation results to be in keeping with the real scenario. Hydrological boring may be used to establish the stratigraphic details of a formation; however, it is challenging to extract the hydrogeological data. The commonly used methods for obtaining hydrogeological parameters are field pumping tests and inversion from the tidal water level (Yuan-ying, 1994). A pumping test will easily destroy the groundwater balance of islands and reefs, while the tidal inversion method needs a large amount of tidal observation data, which is also not easy to achieve.

Geotechnical Engineering about Coral Sand

Coral sand is a special and significant material in geotechnical engineering because of its unique characteristics and behavior. Understanding and applying the fundamentals of soil and rock mechanics to diverse construction and transportation projects is the emphasis of geotechnical engineering. When it comes to engineering uses, coral sand has unique problems and concerns. As was already established, the principal component of coral

sand is the calcium carbonate-rich skeletal remains of coral animals. Compared to other kinds of soil and sand, it has unique engineering features because of its composition. In geotechnical engineering, coral sand has certain important properties that include:

Particle Size and Shape: The grain size of coral sand is normally fine to medium. The individual particles are often asymmetrical and angular, which might have an impact on the material's compaction and shear strength characteristics.

Porosity and Permeability: Coral sand has a complex structure that gives it high porosity and permeability due to its linked pores and blank spaces. In contrast to denser soils, this indicates that water may pass through it more readily. When considering drainage and seepage in geotechnical projects, these properties are crucial.

Settlement and Consolidation: Coral sand may settle and consolidate under stress, much as other soils do. Designing foundations for buildings that will be erected on coral sand requires an understanding of the material's settling behavior and compressibility.

Figure 1. Coral Sand

Strength and Stiffness: Coral sand's strength and stiffness are influenced by things including

particle size, shape, and compaction. Coral sand typically has strong frictional properties and shear resistance owing to its angular particle structure. However, elements like the presence of organic materials or cementation may have an impact on the strength.

Drainage and Permeability: Coral sand's linked pore structure contributes to its excessive porosity and permeability. This makes it advantageous for applications where drainage and seepage management are crucial, such as foundation systems or coastal protection projects.

Coastal Protection and Erosion Control: Coral sand is often utilized in efforts to prevent erosion and safeguard coastlines. Water can flow through because of its porous nature, which lowers the power of waves and prevents erosion along the shore. It may be used in coastal stabilization and protection constructions, including rocks, dams, and revetments.

Engineers must take into account coral sand's special characteristics and reactivity while dealing with it in geotechnical engineering projects to guarantee secure and stable designs. Compaction, drainage, permeability, and shear strength are a few examples of aspects that must be meticulously considered and included in the design process. If necessary, methods like soil stabilization or enhancement may be used to improve coral sand's engineering capabilities. It's crucial to remember that coral sand is often discovered in coastal places, especially in tropical climates where coral reefs flourish. However, the removal of coral sand for engineering reasons is strictly controlled or outright forbidden in many countries owing to environmental concerns and the need to safeguard fragile ecological systems.

Research status of the Coral sand

Coral sand, commonly referred to as coral debris, is a form of silt made up of broken coral bone fragments. It is the result of erosion, wave action, and natural coral development processes. Coral sand is created when the skeletons of dead corals gradually disintegrate into smaller fragments over time. Coral reef ecosystems

depend on coral sand to operate and stay healthy. For a variety of marine creatures, including crustaceans, algae, and tiny fish, it supplies crucial habitats and niches. These creatures find refuge, food, and reproduction in the intricate physical structure of coral sand.

Additionally, coral sand helps keep coral reef systems generally stable. It aids in the processes of water filtration, wave attenuation, and nutrient cycling. The variety and distribution of various benthic creatures, as well as the development and settling of new corals, may all be impacted by the makeup and properties of coral sand. It's important to keep in mind that coral sand studies could have evolved since my last update. For the most up-to-date research status and discoveries on this subject, I advise checking more current scientific publications, academic databases, or speaking with specialists in the area. Coral sand has been the subject of several studies due to its significance in understanding past and present coral reef ecosystems, coastal processes, and paleoenvironmental reconstructions. So here I discuss about coral sand research status:

Paleoceanography and Paleoclimate: Deposits of coral sand may provide important details about historical ocean conditions and climatic change. In order to recreate historical sea surface temperatures, ocean circulation patterns, and changes in atmospheric conditions, scientists examine the chemical composition and isotopic traces of coral sand.

Coastal Processes: For coastal management and conservation, it is crucial to understand the dynamics of coral sand migration and deposition. In order to create models that can forecast coastal erosion and deposition, research is conducted to identify the variables that affect sediment flow, such as wave and current patterns.

Coral Reef Ecology: Our knowledge of coral reef ecosystems is aided by the study of coral sand. As changes in sediment composition and amount may affect reef development, species diversity, and overall ecosystem functioning, they aid in determining the health and vitality of coral reefs.

Geological History: Coral sand deposits may shed light on a location's geological past. In order to understand the age, formation mechanisms, and variations in sea level through time, geologists examine the sedimentary layers, which help to recreate the Earth's history.

Depositional Environments: Coral reefs are prevalent in tropical and subtropical climates, where coral sand is largely created. To comprehend the mechanisms involved in reef formation and degradation, geologists investigate the settings where coral sand is deposited. This study aids in determining historical sea levels, coastal dynamics, and modifications to sedimentation patterns.

Stratigraphy: Deposits of coral sand provide important data for stratigraphic research. To ascertain the order of sediment deposition and its link to other geological formations, geologists examine the layers of coral sand. This helps to determine a region's geological history and rebuild previous habitats.

Diagenesis: Diagenesis describes the alterations that sediments go through after being first deposited. Geologists research the diagenetic processes, such as compaction, cementation, and dissolution, that have an impact on coral sand. The maintenance of coral reef ecosystems and the evolution of coral sand through time may both be explained through a comprehension of these processes.

Geohazards and Coastal Management: Research on coral sand is important for evaluating geohazards and developing coastal management plans. Geologists examine the resilience to erosion and stability of coral sand deposits along the shore. This information aids in the creation of efficient coastal protection strategies, such as beach replenishment, erosion management, and the detection of possible geological hazards.

Characteristics of Coral Sand

Wang et al. (2016) investigated the shape characteristics of coral sand produced from the South China Sea, and the macroscopic and

mesoscopic characteristics of coral sand with particle size of 0.5-5 mm in Wang et al.'s research. Leading to the overall shape of coral sand is far different from silica sand with relative roundness feature. In addition, the rough surface

characteristics of coral sand can be apparently observed from resulting in its specific localized characteristics that need to be considered when analyzing the physical and mechanical performance of coral sand,

Figure 2. Macroscopic - and Mesoscopic Characteristics of Coral Sands Produced from South China Sea Islands: a) Coral Sands with Different Sizes After; b) Typical Coral Sands After; c) Shape Characteristics of an Individual Coral Sand

Furthermore, Wang et al. (2021) pointed out that the shape parameters of coral sand, i.e., overall profile coefficient, angularity and roughness, are associated with the particle size, that is, the larger the size of coral sand, the more complex the particle profile and surface roughness. Therefore, for the particle modeling of coral sand, which is significantly important to the grain-level reactions between coral sands, such as friction, collision, fragmentation, and instability of the sand particulate system, both the overall particle and localized roughness should be taken into consideration. In other words, traditional regular geometry models (e.g., circle, sphere and ellipsoid) or simple polyhedrons (e.g., tetrahedron, hexahedron and

dodecahedron) are hard to describe the shape characteristics of coral sand accurately. As a result, it is necessary to construct a realistic particle model that takes into account both the global and local form characteristics of genuine coral sands.

Interaction of the Particles

Bolton et al. (2008) explored the causes for microscopic mechanical behaviors of soil through DEM simulation of irregular agglomerates of bonded balls. Wang and Coop (2020) conducted single-particle compression tests on crushable sand, concluding that local roundness of a particle has a great effect on its

crushing strength, while other factors concerning the overall shape of the particle, such as equancy, 2D sphericity, and irregularity, had little effect on its crushing strength. Dealing with both artificial and natural particles, Cavarretta et alio (2017) conducted physical tests, applied Hertzian analysis, and used numerical simulations. He proposed a particle failure criterion that considers particle roundness and elastic and plastic features while discussing the relationship between particle crushing strength and size, roundness, and stress induced within. When it comes to the effect of shape on coral sand particles' breakage, however, there have been few studies. Multiple consolidated-drained triaxial shear experiments on coral sand across various circumstances were carried out to ascertain the impact of limiting pressure and dimension on the shear properties of coral sand. To quantify the impact of constraint on the strain-softening and diffusion properties of coral sand with various particle sizes, the stress-softening coefficient and diffusion coefficient were developed. It was discovered that the evolution rules of coral sand's shear strength and strength parameters change with particle size. To study coral sand particle breaking under various circumstances and its impact on coral sand's macroscopic mechanical behavior, the particle survival statistic was developed. The findings of research aid in understanding coral sand's shear properties.

In order to portray coral sand, a 3D random particle model with configurable form and size configurations is built. This model shows the grain-level properties of coral sand in three dimensions, such as rough texture, convex shape, and random size. This section proposes and introduces a number of generating and controlling algorithms for both the particulate system and the individual particle. A unique 3D random particle model with specified form configurations would be chosen to replicate the coral sand grain created from the South China Sea based on the morphological features of coral sand in the literature Wang et al. (2022).

So, in a number of disciplines, including sedimentology, coastal management, and civil engineering it is essential to comprehend how

coral sand particles interact. It assists in the design of foundations, stability evaluation, sediment transport modeling, and forecasting of sand-based system behavior in both natural and manmade contexts.

Calculation Method of Coral Sand

Any scientific or engineering investigation must include a calculating technique since it offers a systematic way to measure and assess different factors, properties, and behaviors. It entails using mathematical and statistical methods to analyze data, forecast the future, or resolve challenging issues. Numerous academic fields, including physics, chemistry, engineering, economics, and many more, utilize calculation techniques. A calculating method's main goal is to guarantee the precision, dependability, and consistency of numerical outputs. Usually, it comprises a set of actions or stages that direct the user through the computations required, accounting for pertinent equations, formulae, or models unique to the issue at hand. For these techniques to provide the desired results or answers, measurable or known values may need to be supplied along with the modification of variables. Iterative procedures are often used in calculation techniques, where starting estimations or assumptions are improved depending on the data gained until an acceptable result is attained. To simplify complicated processes or mimic real-world habits, they may also include theoretical models, computer algorithms, or empirical correlations.

Calculation techniques carefully assess the underlying ideas, presumptions, and limits related to the issue being investigated in addition to the numerical components. Understanding the context and any potential uncertainties or calculation mistakes is necessary for the findings to be properly interpreted. Rigid scientific principles, experimental results, theoretical frameworks, and computing methods are all necessary for the creation of calculating methods. They often serve as sources for scientists, engineers, and professionals in related professions because they are well documented in

scientific literature, textbooks, engineering manuals, or industry standards.

In general, computation techniques are essential for expanding scientific understanding, facilitating engineering design, and supporting decision-making. They provide complicated phenomena with an organized and methodical methodology for quantification and analysis, enabling accurate forecasting, efficiency, and problem-solving across a variety of fields.

Calculation Materials

The uncemented marine sediment used in this study's examination of coral sand was taken from the dredger-filled island reef at a depth ranging from 0 to 17.71 meters below the surface of the planet. After air-drying the specimens, elliptical filters with mesh sizes of 5.0, 2.0, 1.0, 0.5, 0.25, and 0.075 mm were employed for experiment filtering in order to investigate the impact of particle size on the shear properties of coral sand. With particle size ranges of 0.075-0.25, 0.25-0.50, 0.50-1.0, 1.0-2.0, and 2.0-5.0 mm, respectively, fine coral sand, medium coral sand, medium coral sand, coarse coral sand, and gravelly coral sand and designated d1, d2, d3, d4, and d5 (Table 1). The four kinds of specimens were believed to be equally graded coral sand due to the non-significant variations in coral sand's particle size between every single particle size category. The nonuniformity values (C_u) of these samples were 1.95, 1.45, 1.45, and 1.65, respectively, while the curvature coefficients (C_c) were 0.98, 0.96, 0.96, and 0.96 (Table 1). Their average particle diameters (D_{50}) were 0.16, 0.38, 0.75, 1.50, and 3.50 mm. According to the Chinese National Standard of Soil Test Procedures GB/T50123 (Chinese Ministry of Water Resources, 2019), the physical characteristics of coral sand with various particle sizes (such as specific gravity, maximum/minimum dry density, and maximum/minimum void ratio) were measured. (Table 1) shows that, with the exception of particular gravity, there were substantial changes in the physical characteristics of coral sand with varying particle sizes (such as dry density and void ratio) (Lv et al., 2019). Geomaterials have

an intrinsic property called particular gravity, and the value of this property solely relies on the kinds and ratios of the minerals that make up the geomaterials. In this investigation, drill core samples of coral sand from the island reef's dredger fill layer were taken at the same depth and had five different sizes of particles. The specimens' specific gravities were constant because they had the same material structure and comparable mineral ratios. The scattering X-ray spectra of coral sand with tiny particles. Aragonite, calcite, and magnetic calcite were the main minerals found in coral sand. Coral sand had a $CaCO_3$ level exceeding 95% because $CaCO_3$ was the main chemical component of aragonite, calcite, and magnesian calcite. The main chemical components of coral sand and terrigenous quartz sand, consequently, were $CaCO_3$ and SiO_2 . The specific gravity of coral sand (2.73) is higher than that of terrigenous quartz sand (2.65) because the density of $CaCO_3$ tends to be higher than that of terrigenous quartz sand (Wang et al, 2019b).

Consolidated drained triaxial shear experiments were performed on coral sand under various conditions to examine the effects of particle size and applied pressure on the shear characteristics of coral sand. The coral sand was then subjected to screening in order to determine how particle breakage changed with particle size and effective pressure. After receiving vibroflotation treatment, the coral sand used as the foundation material showed a relative density ranging from 60% to 95%, according to a field study on the foundation of an island reef filled by dredgers in the South China Sea. For the development of island reefs, it is crucial to understand how particle size and applied pressure affect the shear properties of coral sand in a condition that is moderately dense and undesirable for the safety of structures. Thus, a relative density of 60% was used for the triaxial shear testing using coral sand of various particle sizes. The extra load placed on the coral sand serving as the foundation soil is generally under 200 kPa due to the modest height of structures on the island reef. The base extra loads imposed by the tallest structures on the island reef, such as the maritime lighthouse and signal tower, are below 400 kPa. Thus, a

relative density of 60% was used for the triaxial shear testing using coral sand of various particle sizes. The extra load placed on the coral sand serving as the foundation soil is generally under 200 kPa due to the modest height of structures

on the island reef. The base extra loads imposed by the tallest structures on the island reef, such as the maritime lighthouse and signal tower, do not exceed 400 kPa.

Figure 3. Location of the Study Area: a) Location of Nansha Islands; b) Hydraulic Reclamation Site; c) The Distribution of Island Reef Sedimentary Zones, Nansha Area, South China Sea

Figure 4. Particle size distribution curves of coral sand with different particle sizes
Source: Bulletin of Engineering Geology and the Environment (2022)

Table 1. Physical properties of coral sand with varying particle sizes

Sample	Sample number	D_{50} (mm)	C_u	C_c	Particle size D (mm)	Specific gravity G_s	Minimum dry density ρ_{dmin} (g/cm ³)	Maximum dry density ρ_{dmax} (g/cm ³)	Minimum void ratio e_{min}
Fine coral sand	d_1	0.16	1.95	0.98	0.075–0.25	2.73	1.08	1.30	1.10
Medium coral sand I	d_2	0.38	1.45	0.96	0.25–0.5	2.73	0.93	1.18	1.32
Medium coral sand II	d_3	0.75	1.45	0.96	0.5–1.0	2.73	0.86	1.17	1.33
Coarse coral sand	d_4	1.50	1.45	0.96	1.0–2.0	2.73	0.83	1.20	1.28
Gravelly coral sand	d_5	3.50	1.65	0.96	2.0–5.0	2.73	0.80	1.33	1.06

The authors eventually combined vacuum saturation method and back-pressure saturation method to achieve specimen saturation (Wang et al., 2019a). The vacuum saturation procedure was run for 2.0 hours, and the back pressures for the various specimens were adjusted to 300 kPa during the back-pressure saturation. This allowed for an easy comparison of the test findings. The specimens were 120 mm in height and 61.8 mm in diameter. Coral sand calculation techniques are essential for understanding the behavior and characteristics of this material in engineering applications. These techniques

include shear strength, settlement, stress-strain behavior, and stability evaluations, among other investigations. These calculations help engineers and researchers make well-informed judgments on the design, functionality, and environmental effect of coral sand-based structures by identifying critical factors and features. The reliability and precision of these estimates are guaranteed by following the right standards and procedures, encouraging the safe and long-term usage of coral sand in a variety of engineering projects.

Figure 5. XRD Test Results of the Coral Sand: a) XRD Pattern; b) Mineral Composition and Proportion
Source: Bulletin of Engineering Geology and the Environment (2022)

Test Equipment and Calculation Method of Coral Sand

Understanding and assessing coral sand's activity and qualities in diverse projects requires the use of calculation techniques. Coral sand has distinct properties that call for specialist calculations. It is made up of components from shattered coral reefs. In order to construct structures, evaluate environmental consequences, and ensure long-term performance, these methodologies strive to measure factors including strength, settlement, stability, and deformation.

Collecting representative coral sand samples from the target site is crucial to start with. In order to maintain their natural condition and reduce any change or disruption, these samples should be properly collected. To acquire a thorough knowledge of the coral sand, numerous attributes must be examined when the samples are gathered. Grain size distribution, moisture content, density, porosity, and specific gravity are some of these characteristics. Further computations are based on these essential properties. Finding out the coral sand's index qualities is very important next. Natural water content, Atterberg limits (liquid limit, plastic limit, and plasticity index), and grain size analyses are all measured in the lab. These characteristics enable coral sand categorization and shed light

on its engineering performance. Evaluating the shear strength of coral sand is one of the important components of the analysis. To ascertain shear strength parameters, laboratory procedures like direct shear, triaxial shear, or simple shear tests are carried out. These variables often include cohesion (c) and the friction angle (φ). They are essential to comprehending coral sand's stability and behavior under various loading scenarios. In addition to shear strength, coral sand's consolidation properties must be evaluated. Consolidation tests provide details on the behavior of the sand under load in terms of settling and time-dependent deformation. The findings of the consolidation test may be used to compute parameters like the coefficient of consolidation (c_v), the coefficient of volume compressibility (c_v), and the compression index (c_i). For calculating settlement and comprehending the long-term behavior of buildings erected on coral sand, these characteristics are critical.

Stress-strain analysis is used to examine the stress-strain behavior of coral sand. In this research, the stress-strain relationship and elastic modulus of the coral sand are determined using laboratory experiments or empirical relationships. It aids in comprehending how the sand reacts to various loading scenarios and

offers insightful information for design and stability analyses. Analyzing coral sand requires careful consideration of settlement estimates. Settlement describes the sand's vertical compression or deformation under stress. Coral sand settlement may be approximated by taking into account variables like the applied stress, the depth of the sand layer, and the consolidation qualities discovered by laboratory studies. Settlement may be calculated using approaches like one-dimensional consolidation theory or numerical modeling.

Another essential use of coral sand calculation technique is stability analysis. It entails evaluating the stability of buildings constructed on or with coral sand while taking slope stability, bearing capacity, and foundation design into account. To ascertain the stability of the structure under different loading situations, the shear strength parameters, stress distribution, and deformation properties of the sand are assessed. It is crucial to keep in mind that coral sand calculation techniques require a thorough examination of the underlying concepts, presumptions, and restrictions unique to this material. Coral sand shows distinctive behaviors as a result of its content and development, and as such, these traits must be taken into consideration in the calculations. When applying coral sand calculation techniques in engineering investigations, it's also important to obey any local laws, standards, or business conventions.

A fully automated triaxial stress path tester was used for the tests, and it included five different components: a data collection system, a pressure chamber, a strain-control system, a back-pressure control system, and a confining-pressure control system. The triaxial shear apparatus could accomplish variable-rate loading since the shear rate varied and ranged from 0.0001 to 1.2 mm/min. The accuracy of the axial load sensor was 0.15% F.S., with a range of 15 KN. The stress control range and accuracy for the back-pressure and confining-pressure control systems are 0-2.0 MPa and 1.0 KPa, respectively. Preparations before testing, specimen preparation, testing, and particle breakage measurement were the four phases of the test.

Coral sand with various particle sizes was dried to a consistent mass at a constant temperature of 105 °C prior to testing, and it was then placed in a drying tank to cool to room temperature. Then, coral sand specimens with different particle sizes were configured according to equations. (1) and (2):

$$\rho_d = \frac{G_s}{1+e_0} = \frac{G_s}{1+[e_{\max}-Dr \times (e_{\max}-e_{\min})]} \quad (1)$$

$$m = V\rho_d \quad (2)$$

where ρ_d , e_0 , m , and V are the dry density, void ratio, mass, and volume of the specimen, respectively.

The drop accumulation approach was used to layer the specimen onto a rubber membrane in three layers after cutting it into three equal pieces. The specimen surface was gently compacted with a sample tamper after a coating of coral sand was placed, and the specimen height was then measured using a graduated scale to see whether it matched the design criteria for compactness. Repeating this procedure allowed the specimen to reach a height of 120 mm. Coral sand is a unique geomaterial that, when subjected to modest stress, may undergo particle breaking (Zhang et al., 2005). The specimen surfaces shouldn't be aggressively pounded in order to prevent particle breakage from impacting the test findings.

The specimen was saturated using a combination of the vacuum saturation technique and the back-pressure saturation method. The specimen's B value reached 95%, indicating that it had attained saturation; otherwise, the specimens were retested using the aforementioned process. After saturation, the specimen underwent an isotropic consolidation test until the change in back pressure volume during five minutes did not exceed five millimeters (mm) in volume. Triaxial shear tests were carried out on the specimens until the axial strain reached 20% at a shear rate of 0.6 mm/min.

Coral sand was taken from the rubber membrane during the triaxial shear test, baked in an oven, screened after returning to normal temperature, and its particle size distribution was examined. According to related study findings

Zhang et al. (2022a), the screen test length significantly affects the particle breakup of coral sand. The screen test was given a 15-minute time limit to avoid having an impact on the test findings (Zhang et al., 2005).

Figure 6. Fully Automated Triaxial Stress Path Tester

The Advantages of Modern Calculation Technology

When used for the investigation and evaluation of coral sand, contemporary computation technology provides a number of important benefits. These developments have significantly improved the comprehension and use of this special substance in numerous technical applications. In this paragraph, we shall discuss the benefits of contemporary computation technology for coral sand. The capability of contemporary calculating technology to handle

complicated data linked to coral sand qualities is one of its main benefits. Large datasets were difficult for traditional techniques to handle and evaluate, which limited the level of comprehension. However, it is now feasible to analyze enormous volumes of data effectively because of current computing tools, such as sophisticated modeling and simulation software. With the use of this skill, scientists and engineers may get a thorough grasp of coral sand's physical and mechanical characteristics, including its grain size distribution, moisture content, density, porosity, and permeability. For the purpose of

developing structures and determining how coral sand will behave in different engineering projects, it is essential to analyze these qualities. Another benefit is the capacity of contemporary computing technology to predict and model the behavior of coral sand in various situations. A virtual environment for investigating how coral sand responds to loads from outside sources, environmental changes, and other variables is provided through computer-based simulations. Researchers can mimic the mechanical behavior, settlement features, and deformation patterns of coral sand formations by using sophisticated numerical approaches. Engineers may use these models to create accurate projections and design improvements that result in more dependable and efficient buildings that are constructed on or using coral sand.

Modern computation technology also offers the benefits of efficiency and speed. Calculations that formerly required a lot of time and effort may now be completed quickly because of the availability of powerful computer resources and efficient algorithms. This effectiveness enables researchers and engineers to carry out parametric analyses, evaluate various design scenarios, and examine large-scale coral sand projects. Decision-making processes are greatly accelerated, and productivity is increased through quick computations and data processing. Modern mathematical technology further improves the accuracy and precision of coral sand analysis. Human error is common in manual computations, which may have serious repercussions in engineering projects. However, the possibility of mistakes is reduced by automated computation tools and software. Advanced numerical techniques and algorithms provide accurate computations and trustworthy outcomes. This precision is essential for figuring out coral sand's stability, settlement, and deformation properties, which enable the design and building of secure and long-lasting structures.

The adaptability of contemporary calculating technologies to handling diverse facets of coral sand analysis is another benefit. The incorporation of many analytical approaches and methodologies is made possible by the ability to

customize calculation tools and software to meet certain needs. For instance, geotechnical engineering-specific software programs may provide complete solutions for assessing coral sand behavior, including consolidation analysis, evaluations of slope rigidity, and foundation construction. Due to its adaptability, coral sand evaluation may be analyzed by engineers and scientists from a variety of perspectives, leading to a deeper comprehension of the material's characteristics and function.

The availability of contemporary computing technology also makes it easier to collaborate and spread information in the area of coral sand analysis. More professionals can now access and efficiently use calculation software and instruments thanks to their increased user friendliness. Because of this ease of access, specialists are more likely to collaborate and share information, which promotes innovation. Additionally, it encourages multidisciplinary cooperation among coastal biologists, environmental scientists, and geotechnical engineers, providing comprehensive method of coral sand investigation.

Numerical Method

Numerical investigations were conducted on both Toyoura sand and coral sand, utilizing particles with identical gradation. The average particle size was 0.17 mm, and the uniformity coefficient measured 1.7. Key physical properties of both sand types are summarized in Table 1. To simulate their stress-strain relationship, the hypoplastic constitutive model (HP model) was employed. The hypoplastic model is an advanced constitutive model, which was first proposed by Kolymbas (1991) to describe the complex mechanical response of granular material, and then incorporated critical state theory, stress and state dependency, intergranular strain, strain-dependency, and stress history effects. In this study, the hypoplastic model proposed by von Wolersdor (1996) was adopted to describe the stress-strain relationship of coral sand and silica sand, which established the relationship between the stress rate tensor

and the strain rate tensor to capture soil behaviors both reversible and irreversible deformations, as follows:

$$\dot{\sigma} = f_h f_e [L(\hat{\sigma}, e) : \dot{\epsilon} + f_d N(\hat{\sigma}, e) \|\dot{\epsilon}\|] \quad (3)$$

where $\hat{\sigma}$ is the stress ratio tensor and has the value $\sigma/tr\sigma$. Both L and N are functions of soil conditions, and they are both constitutive tensors. The linear component in the first section of the $L(\hat{\sigma}, e)\dot{\epsilon}$ indicates that the stress

rises linearly with strain. In the second section $(N(\hat{\sigma}, e)\|\dot{\epsilon}\|)$ the nonlinear connection between stress increase and strain increment is established. Sand's dependence on pressure, as shown by the barotropy factor f_b , may be identified through isotropic compression. The density dependence of sand was represented by the scalar components f_e and f_d . In a triaxial test, it was discovered that f_d controlled the sand's dilatancy, or the height of the peak stress, while f_e governed the strain corresponding to the peak stress, or the location of the peak point.

Table 2. Physical Properties of Coral Sand and Silica Sand

Physical properties	Coral sand	Toyoura sand
Particle density, ρ_s (g/cm ³)	2.7	2.64
Maximum dry density, $\rho_{d\ max}$ (g/cm ³)	1.55	1.64
Minimum dry density, $\rho_{d\ min}$ (g/cm ³)	1.22	1.33
Maximum void ratio, e_{max}	1.28	0.997
Minimum void ratio, e_{min}	0.79	0.597

Even without the yield surface or flow rule of the conventional elastic-plastic constitutive model, it is possible to implement the automated judgment of loading and unloading by inserting the Euclidean norm of the strain rate tensor into the nonlinear term. Eight fundamental material parameters, (i.e., $\varphi_s, h_s, n, e_{d0}, e_{d0}, e_{d0}, a,$ and β) as well as an additional five parameters (i.e., $m_R, m_T, R, \beta_s,$ and χ), account for strain- and stress-dependent stiffness at small strains. A user-defined function in the program Abaqus has implemented the model. This work directly accepted the model parameters for Toyoura and coral sand that had been established by Hong et al., (2016) and Wang et al. (2021), respectively.

When used to analyze and assess coral sand, modern computation technology offers a number of benefits. It provides realistic coral sand behavior modeling and simulation, effective processing and analysis of complicated data, and increased computation velocity, precision, and flexibility.

The Shortages of Modern Calculation Technology

The absence of comprehensive and complete data regarding coral sand is one of the key deficiencies. Calculation techniques depend significantly on input quantities and attributes obtained from lab testing or field observations. However, owing to its limited availability, variation in different places, and challenges in sample collection, collecting accurate statistics on coral sand may be difficult. In certain circumstances, it may be difficult to adequately capture the complete spectrum of behavior and properties of coral sand since investigators may have to depend on small datasets.

The problem is the absence of known constitutive models that are especially made for coral sand. Constitutive models are mathematical depictions that explain how materials behave mechanically. While there are well-established models for typical soils and rocks, coral sand's unique composition and structure make it challenging to create dependable and accurate models. Existing models might not adequately capture the

complex interactions between coral particles, cementing agents, and vacuum spaces in the sand. Due to this restriction, it may be difficult to accurately forecast how coral sand would behave and react under various loading and environmental scenarios.

Another important need is the computational difficulty of modeling coral sand behavior. Coral sand has complex particle connections, such as particle breaking and interconnection, which may result in nonlinear and discontinuous behavior. Advanced computational approaches, such as particle-based methods, discrete element modeling, or other sophisticated numerical simulations, are required to capture these intricacies. These techniques may, however, be computationally time and resource-consuming in order to get useful findings. Due to this restriction, it is difficult to carry out comprehensive parametric analyses or large-scale simulations for coral sand analysis.

Furthermore, there is a problem with a shortage of reliable calibration and validation data for coral sand models. In order to guarantee the precision and dependability of computational models, calibration and validation are essential processes. However, the calibration and validation of models become difficult since there aren't many thorough experimental data sets available for coral sand. Without reliable calibration and validation, there is a chance of either overfitting or underestimating the model uncertainties, which might result in inaccurate predictions and analyses.

Obstacle is the unpredictability of coral sand's behavior and qualities. Because coral sand is a naturally occurring substance with intrinsic spatial and temporal diversity, it is challenging to adequately describe its characteristics and behavior. Uncertainties in its mechanical characteristics are caused by differences in particle size, shape, cementing agents, and biological variables.

Despite its strengths, modern computation technology may find it difficult to fully account for these uncertainties, which might result in projections that are either too cautious or too enthusiastic. Strong probabilistic methods and

sensitivity assessments are needed to deal with uncertainties, and coral sand analysis may provide extra difficulties. Finally, a major worry is the shortage of expertise and experience in employing contemporary computation technologies for coral sand analysis. Analyzing coral sand requires a thorough grasp of both computational techniques and the unique properties and behavior of coral sand. However, it may be difficult to find professionals who are knowledgeable in both fields. The shortage of multidisciplinary knowledge and cooperation between geotechnical engineers, materials scientists, and computational modelers might impede the broad use and development of calculation methods for coral sand analysis.

There are drawbacks and restrictions when it comes to studying coral sand, despite the fact that contemporary computation technology has many benefits. These include difficulties with data accessibility, constitutive modeling, complicated computations, calibration and validation, uncertainty, and expertise. Further study, data gathering, model creation, and cooperation among specialists from many sectors are all necessary to address these shortfalls. By overcoming these constraints, coral sand analysis may be made more precise and trustworthy, and its usage in different engineering applications can be made more efficient and sustainable.

Constriction Foundation of Coral Sand

Coral sand construction foundation refers to the use of coral sand as a material for building foundations in construction projects. Sand that is made from the skeleton remnants of coral reefs is known as coral sand and has special qualities. In coastal regions with a lot of coral formations, it is often employed. The tremendous load-bearing capability of coral sand makes it an excellent choice for building foundations. Coral sand has exceptional stability and can successfully sustain massive construction because its particles are compressed. Coral sand also offers high drainage

qualities, allowing for effective water permeability and preventing waterlogging and possible foundation damage. The endurance of coral sand for building foundations is an additional advantage. Coral sand is appropriate for long-term usage in coastal areas where exposure to seawater and severe weather conditions is common since it is inherently resistant to erosion and deterioration. The coral sand's interlocking structure also adds to the foundation's stability and resistance to lateral stresses. Therefore, coral sand construction foundations provide a trustworthy and long-lasting option for constructing buildings in coastal locations. Coral sand foundations provide a sturdy platform for building projects while taking into account the requirement for environmental sustainability because of their excellent load-bearing capacity, superior drainage capabilities, and resistance to erosion.

Problems of the Coral Sand Foundation

Any construction project needs a foundation because it offers stability and support. However, there are a number of particular issues and difficulties with coral sand foundations that must be resolved. Coral sand offers particular problems that call for careful attention in engineering design and building procedures due to its unique composition and features. We'll go through some of the major issues with coral sand foundations.

The possibility of settling and distortion is one of the main issues with coral sand foundations. Coral sand often has hollow areas and is loosely packed, which may cause settling when subjected to weight. The presence of coral fragments and a dispersed pattern of particle sizes make this issue worse. Uneven settlement throughout the foundation from settlement may result in a structural failure and equal damages to the sustained structure. It is essential to calculate the settlement correctly and put suitable safeguards in place to minimize its impact.

The unevenness and variety of coral sand deposits are also serious issues. Coral sand is

created by natural processes, and the size, shape, content, and cementation of the grains may all vary significantly. These changes may cause uneven settlement and non-uniform load distribution, as well as geographically and temporally varied foundation characteristics. To guarantee the durability and longevity of buildings, it is crucial to take these variances into account and comprehend how they affect foundation function.

A problem with coral sand foundations is connected to their geotechnical characteristics. Coral sand's rigidity and strength may vary greatly based on elements including grain properties, cementation, and the presence of natural components. For the design and study of coral sand foundations, the precise determination of geotechnical parameters such as shear strength, bearing capacity, and modulus of elasticity is essential. However, it is difficult to accurately predict these qualities because of the diversity and complexity of coral sand, which creates uncertainty in foundation design and performance.

Additionally, coral sand is prone to scour and erosion, especially in coastal and marine areas. The degradation of the sand particles by the wave and current action might result in the loss of foundation support. Structures constructed on coral sand may lose their structural strength as a result of this subsidence, which may also compromise their rigidity. For coral sand foundations to be stable and safe over the long term in these conditions, erosion and scour threats must be properly assessed and mitigated.

For foundations, the possibility of marine animals in coral sand, such as corals and shells, might be problematic. These organisms may help cement sand particles, increasing the sand's stability and strength. They may, however, also leave gaps and weak spots in the sand, weakening its overall integrity and strength. To comprehend their influence on the functionality and lifespan of the foundation, the connection between marine species and it must be thoroughly addressed.

Construction and excavation provide unique difficulties for coral sand foundations. Coral

sand is loose and unconsolidated, which may make excavation and boring challenging and require the use of specific methods and tools. Furthermore, due to the delicate and sensitive nature of coral ecological systems, the environmental effects of building operations must be carefully taken into account. In order to minimize disruptions to the coral habitat and preserve the stability of the foundation, proper planning and execution of the building operations are crucial.

Lastly, there is a serious issue with the absence of design standards and best practices for coral sand foundations. Coral sand is a special kind of material with unique properties; therefore, traditional design methods may not be completely appropriate. The absence of explicit recommendations and best practices may result in cautious designs, unneeded expenditures, or possible design flaws. To provide thorough design standards and suggestions specifically for coral sand foundations, further study, data gathering, and information exchange are required.

A variety of issues and difficulties with coral sand foundations must be taken into consideration throughout engineering design and construction procedures. Some of the main issues with coral sand foundations are settlement and deformation, non-uniformity and variability, erosion and scour concerns, marine life interactions, building challenges, and the absence of design requirements. In order to guarantee the durability, safety, and lifespan of buildings erected on coral sand foundations, it is necessary to fully comprehend the special properties of coral sand and to execute suitable design, construction, and monitoring approaches.

Treatment Method of the Coral Sand Foundation

The special qualities and difficulties of coral sand foundations must be carefully taken into account while treating them. Coral sand has several drawbacks, but there are a number of solutions that may be used to improve the efficiency and

durability of foundations constructed with it. We'll go through some of the most important foundational therapy options. Ground enhancement methods are a typical solution for coral sand foundations. These methods seek to improve the soil's structural qualities, such as strength, stiffness, and permeability. Compression is an often-used technique for improving the ground. Coral sand's loose and unconsolidated character may be improved by compacting it, increasing its density, and lowering its permeability. Mechanical compaction techniques, such as dynamic compaction or vibratory rollers, which compress the soil layers by energy transfer, may accomplish compaction. Alternately, preloading and surcharge procedures may be used, in which more weight is put on the foundation region for a particular period of time to promote settling and fusion before the real building is built. The coral sand foundation's overall stability is improved, and settlement is reduced, thanks to these ground repair techniques.

Soil stabilization is another technique for caring for coral sand foundations. This method includes modifying the coral sand's characteristics to increase its durability, cohesiveness, and erosion susceptibility. Chemical stabilization and soil reinforcement are two stabilization techniques that may be employed. Coral sand may be strengthened and stabilized by chemical stabilization by adding chemicals like lime, cement, or chemical grouts. These substances interact with the soil particles to improve their bonding and shear strength. In order to increase the coral sand's load-bearing capacity and lessen deformation, soil reinforcing methods include the incorporation of geosynthetic materials, such as geotextiles or geogrids, into the coral sand. The stability of the foundation is improved by these materials' increased tensile strength and more uniform load distribution.

Strategies for controlling groundwater and drainage are crucial in the treatment of coral sand foundations. Coral sand is vulnerable to problems with water, such as erosion, pore water pressure building, and liquefaction. The stability of the foundation may be enhanced by using

appropriate drainage systems, such as the construction of horizontal and vertical drains, to absorb excess pore water pressure. By putting in place groundwater management tools like well points or dewatering devices, it is also possible to lower the water table and the risk of instability or erosion. Under a variety of hydrological circumstances, efficient drainage and groundwater management systems aid in preserving the strength and durability of the coral sand foundation.

Additional precautions may be needed to prevent erosion and scour in marine or coastal locations when coral sand foundations are exposed to wave and current activity. The foundation may be shielded from erosive stresses using methods including installing armor layers, using geotextile tubes or concrete mattresses, and applying erosion-resistant coatings. By creating a barrier of protection and assisting in the dissipation of wave energy, these actions reduce the likelihood of coral sand erosion and scouring.

Coral sand foundations must also be continuously maintained and monitored to guarantee their long-term effectiveness. Monitoring methods, such as settlement monitoring, pore pressure readings, and foundation instrumentation, may provide important information on the performance and behavior of the foundation over time. The stability and functioning of the coral sand foundation may be preserved with regular inspections and maintenance procedures, including sediment removal, repair of erosion protection measures, and control of plant development. A variety of methods are used to treat coral sand foundations with the goal of enhancing the material's engineering qualities and strength. Treatment of coral sand foundations includes ground improvement techniques, soil stabilization, drainage and groundwater management, erosion prevention measures, and continuing monitoring and maintenance. Engineers may improve the stability, toughness, and long-term performance of structures constructed on coral sand foundations by putting these treatment

procedures into practice, ensuring their effective integration in a variety of engineering projects.

Mechanical Properties and Durability of Cement Stabilized of the Coral Sand Foundation

In engineering design and building processes, it is crucial to take the mechanical characteristics and toughness of cement-stabilized coral sand foundation into account. Given its special makeup and properties, coral sand necessitates the use of appropriate stabilizing procedures to increase its

Tensile strength, stability and environmental resistance. We shall discuss the mechanical characte-

istics and durability features of cement-stabilized coral sand foundation. A common technique for enhancing coral sand's mechanical characteristics and load-bearing capability is cement stabilization. Calcium silicate and calcium aluminate hydrates are created when cement is combined with coral sand via a process known as hydration. These hydration substances bond the coral sand particles together, increasing the material's overall strength and stiffness.

Compressive strength is one of the main mechanical characteristics impacted by cement stabilization. Cement greatly increases the compressive force of the coral sand mixture, allowing it to support heavier loads without experiencing significant deformation or collapse. The quantity of cement used and the curing circumstances have a significant impact on the compressive strength that is attained. To encourage ideal cement hydration and the creation of high compressive strength, proper curing processes are crucial. These include maintaining optimum moisture and temperature conditions. Coral sand bases with cement stabilization have increased tensile and flexural strength in addition to compressive strength. The coral sand's cementitious matrix strengthens its ability to resist cracking and more uniformly distributes the applied stresses, which lowers the likelihood of isolated failures. The stabilized

coral sand foundation is more stable and durable overall because of its enhanced tensile and flexural strength, which enables it to tolerate external pressures and loading conditions better. The coral sand base's shear strength is another significant mechanical characteristic that is affected by cement stabilization. The coral sand's shear strength is improved by the cement's increased frictional resistance and interparticle bonding. This enhancement is especially important for foundation systems and other applications where the coral sand foundation is exposed to lateral stresses or shear forces. Under these stress conditions, the increased shear strength guarantees the stability and integrity of the coral sand foundation.

When evaluating the long-term performance of cement-stabilized coral sand foundation, durability is a key factor. Being a natural substance, coral sand is subject to a variety of environmental conditions that may eventually compromise its stability and integrity. By shielding the coral sand from the damaging effects of moisture, erosion, and chemical deterioration, cement stabilization significantly improves durability. The capacity of cement-stabilized coral sand foundation to withstand moisture and other water-related problems is one of the main factors impacting their long-term durability. Due to the limited permeability of cementitious materials, water and moisture cannot easily pass through the stabilized foundation. This lessens the possibility of water intrusion and consequent harm; such as frost heave or weakness brought on by saturation. The stabilized foundation is resistance to moisture infiltration is further increased by proper compaction and thorough curing, ensuring long-term durability.

For cement-stabilized coral sand foundations, erosion resistance is a crucial component of durability, especially in coastal or marine situations. The cement's binding properties aid in preventing erosion brought on by wave, current, and tidal pressures, which would otherwise wear away the coral sand particles. By creating a more cohesive and erosion-resistant structure, the stabilized base reduces material loss and preserves the foundation's stability.

The endurance of a cement-stabilized coral sand foundation is also heavily influenced by chemical resistance. Salts, acids, and alkalis are only a few of the various chemical compounds that cementitious materials successfully withstand. This resilience is useful in contexts like industrial or agricultural ones where the coral sand foundation could be subjected to harsh chemical conditions. The structural integrity and long-term performance of the stabilized base are ensured by its resistance to chemical assaults. It is important to note that a number of variables, including the cement quantity, water-cement ratio, curing circumstances, and caliber of the coral sand itself, affect the mechanical capabilities and durability of cement-stabilized coral sand bases. To maximize the functionality and endurance of the stabilized foundation, these aspects must be carefully taken into account throughout the design and construction phases.

Coral sand foundations' mechanical characteristics and durability are considerably increased by cement stabilization. The coral sand's compressive, tensile, flexural, and bending strengths are all improved by the inclusion of cement. In addition to providing long-term durability, cement stabilization increases the coral sand foundation is resistance to moisture, erosion, and chemical deterioration. To provide cement-stabilized coral sand foundation with the appropriate mechanical properties and durability traits, adequate cement content selection, curing techniques, and quality control considerations are crucial.

Mechanical Properties of the Coral Sand Foundation

Foundation on the test findings, the shear stress-shear strain and vertical displacement-shear strain evolution curves between coral sand and various morphological slabs acquired by interface shear testing under various normal stresses.

It can be seen that the development of the stress-strain (τ - ϵ) curves are similar under the different vertical pressure and different

morphology. And the whole process can be divided into four stages:

Initial particle adjustment stage

Partial accumulation of stress may occur at this point (such as interaction between the convex area of the contact surface and the sands) since while the vertical pressure is applied to consolidate, the interaction among the particles and the slab is not strong enough. As a result, the sample's internal structure would change as the shearing process started, resulting in closer contact between the particles and the contact surface.

Additionally, the normal displacement curve (body deformation) revealed that this was the compaction stage. The vertical displacement-strain curve and the stress-strain curve exhibit almost the same tendencies when interacting with various slabs under the same vertical force. The curve is spiraling, the shear stress rises progressively, and compression takes place as the displacement in the vertical direction diminishes. On the other hand, when the same slab interacts with it at various vertical pressures, the higher the vertical pressure, the greater the shear stress, the quicker the growing rate, the greater the vertical displacement, and the more visible the impact of the contraction.

Figure 7. Stress – Strain Relationship: a) and vertical displacement–strain relationship; b) Under Different Slabs (red: interaction with SmS; blue: interaction with CoS; purple: interaction with SaS; A, B, C, D resent feature points in four stages)

Source: J. Cent. South Univ. (2020) 27: 3436–3449

Elastic Deformation Stage

In this stage, when the stress rises quickly as the strain rises and the internal structure of the particles is significantly altered, the stress-strain curves exhibit linear properties. The particles slide and rotate over the structural surface to withstand heavier external loads. This causes the shear stress to increase quickly, which also lessens the impact of the contraction and even starts to exhibit dilatancy, particularly under lower vertical pressure. The greater the value of R_v , when interacting with various slabs under the

same vertical pressure, the greater the shear stress, which is more noticeable at high vertical pressure. When it is applied with SaS, rotation dominates the particle motions, and the highest biting cooperation exists between the particles, leading to a significant rise in shear stress. Particles may slide and roll when they contact CoS; as a result, the shear stress is reduced and there is less sliding friction resistance with the structural surface. When it is used on a SmS, the shearing process solely emphasizes friction between the slab and sand particles. The twirling of particles requires more resistance than the

sliding action. Since the shear force is at its smallest at this point, just a few of the particles are shattered.

Figure 8. Sketch Map of Coral Sand Movement Evolution in Shear Band:
a) Interacting with SaS; (b) Interacting with CoS; (c) Interacting with SmS.

Source: Cent. South Univ. (2020) 27: 3436–3449

Initial yield stage

The internal structure of the sample is complete at this point, and the shear stress increases gradually as the acceleration increases.

A few particles start to break down step by step. Under reduced vertical pressure, the concentrated tension is insufficient to break down the coral sand, and the rotation of the particles results in the diffusion of the sands. On the other hand, with increasing vertical pressure, the coral sand's inherent strength was unable to withstand the intense stress, which led to the onset of fractures where neither diffusion nor the contraction's influence was lessened.

The dilatancy of the sample may be more affected by particle rotation than by sliding or other particle motion. The CoS has a lower loop volume than the SaS while having a lower average relative roughness. The most important

result of the connection between coral sand and COS is the diffusion impact J. Cent. (2020).

Plastic yield stage

The shear band (contact band) has formed after the first yield stage. The strength of sands inside the contact band is also low owing to particle breaking and internal structural adjustment, which causes the deformation to mostly proceed along the contact band while the tension and density stay steady. The fragments across the contact band are more compact because the tiny particles produced following component breaking might potentially fill the pores, preventing strain softening from happening beyond the peak shear strength.

The residual strength, which is roughly equivalent to the peak shear stress when

interacting with various structural surfaces, increases with increasing relative roughness.

In the meantime, under various stress situations, except the vertical stress of 100 kPa, the vertical displacement has remained constant. This is mostly because the structural adjustment between the particles is essentially finished when the particles break under high normal stress. Although the particle breakage is very minimal at low normal stress (100 kPa), the holes between the particles nonetheless enable the particles to continually adapt and evolve.

Overall, the structure is continually changed, and the coral sand particles in the shear band spin and roll at the start of the shearing process, which causes the dilatancy. Some coral sand particles are shattered when the shearing process advances to the yield stage, and the coral sand in the shear zone evolves into a more solid and compact form, leading to the contraction. On the other hand, it's also crucial to take into account the various mechanical response traits based on how structure surfaces of various roughness's are interacted with. Figure 8 illustrates the shear strength of the interaction face between coral sand and three distinct contact surfaces according to the law of fitting curves. The internal friction angles of the smooth steel slab, the rough concrete slab, and the sawtooth steel slab are 34.7°, 36.6°, and 42.2°, respectively, and they match the stress-strain curve, which meets the linear relationship. The coral sand's sliding or rotating over the structure's surface is what primarily causes contact between the two materials. The shear stress and accompanying internal friction angle both increase as the slab's roughness increases because the particles mostly spin on their contact with the surface.

Durability of Cement Stabilized of the Coral Sand Foundation

Engineering applications that call for the use of coral sand for building projects must take the durability of a cement-stabilized coral sand foundation into account. Natural soil components, such as coral sand, may be

strengthened and made to last longer by using cement stabilization. To improve the coral sand's mechanical characteristics and resistance to external conditions, cementitious materials are mixed with it.

The durability of a cement-stabilized coral sand base can be evaluated foundation on several factors:

Compressive Strength: Coral sand's compressive strength is increased by cement stabilization, which also creates a binding matrix and encourages cement hydration. Increased compressive strength suggests longer-lasting structural integrity and better resistance to load-bearing.

Resistance to Moisture: Due to the porous nature of coral sand, it is vulnerable to moisture penetration and subsequent damage from freeze-thaw cycles or swelling-shrinkage processes. Coral sand's resistance to moisture-related deterioration is increased by cement stabilization, which lowers its permeability.

Chemical Stability: Coral sand foundation might come into contact with a variety of chemical substances from the environment, including alkalis, acids, and seawater. By lowering the reactivity of coral sand with these compounds and limiting the possibility of chemical breakdown, cement stabilization offers chemical stability.

Erosion Resistance: In coastal regions, coral sand bottoms may experience wave action, tidal forces, or water flow. By fusing the particles together and lowering the possibility of loss and displacement of particles, cement stabilization increases the coral sand's resilience to erosion.

Long-Term Performance: The long-term performance of a coral sand foundation stabilized with cement is also assessed. Aging, exposure to the environment, and repetitive loading may all have an impact on the base's performance and stability over time. Evaluations over an extended period of time are required to determine how well the cement-stabilized foundation can survive these difficulties.

It is crucial to use the right mix design, construction methods, and quality control

systems when building on cement-stabilized coral sand foundations. The stabilized foundation must be properly cured in order to develop its strength and durability to their full potential. Regular examination and maintenance are also required to spot any indications of discomfort or degradation and take immediate action to stop further harm. The compressive strength, resistance to moisture, chemical stability, erosion resistance, and long-term performance of a cement-stabilized coral sand substrate define its durability. Coral sand foundations are more durable and have improved mechanical qualities, making them appropriate for use in a variety of engineering applications. However, for such foundation to operate and last over the long term, correct mix design, building methods, and continuing maintenance are essential.

Conclusions

In conclusion, there are many different aspects that affect the physical and mechanical characteristics of coral sand. Making judgments on how to use these attributes in engineering and building projects requires an understanding of these characteristics. The usual particle size distribution of coral sand is between silt and gravel, with fine to medium-sized particles making up the majority of the material. Because of this quality, it may be used in certain technical applications where a particular range of particle sizes is necessary. Another noteworthy quality of coral sand is its high porosity, which promotes efficient water permeability and drainage. Coral sand is useful for uses including filtration systems and septic drain fields due to its porosity. When employing coral sand in building projects, density is a crucial factor. Coral sand often has a lower density than other forms of sand. Its reduced density may restrict its usage in certain applications and have an impact on its load-bearing capability. Coral sand may still be used efficiently in non-load-bearing situations like landscaping or beach replenishment projects. Coral sand's strength is affected by things including particle form, packing arrangement, and cementation. Coral sand often

has less strength than denser sands, which makes it unsuitable for applications requiring load-bearing. However, coral pieces in the sand may increase the material's overall strength and stability, particularly if they are tightly bonded together. In engineering analyses, the strength variations brought on by the heterogeneity of coral sand should be properly taken into account. Coral sand is affected significantly by coastal erosion. Coral sand is readily eroded by water and wind because of its great porosity and low density. The loss of beach sediments and the destruction of coastal ecosystems may result from this erosion. When dealing with coral sand in coastal settings, it is essential to comprehend the erosion processes and put suitable erosion control measures in place. In engineering and building applications, coral sand's physical and mechanical characteristics offer both benefits and drawbacks. It is appropriate for several purposes, including filtration systems, septic drain fields, and non-load-bearing structures, because of its porosity and drainage qualities. However, compared to other sands, it has a lower density and strength, which limits its use in load-bearing situations. Its overall strength and stability may be impacted by the coral pieces present and sand heterogeneity. Additionally, particularly in coastal locations, it is important to properly regulate coral sand's erosion susceptibility. The particular characteristics of coral sand may vary greatly depending on the kind of coral, the surrounding environment, and the location. Therefore, in order to appropriately evaluate the characteristics of coral sand in a given context, site-specific testing and analysis must be carried out. Since coral sand has a variety of physical and mechanical characteristics, it is important to understand them in order to use them properly in engineering and building. Its porosity, density, strength, presence of coral pieces, and susceptibility to erosion should all be carefully taken into account. Engineers and designers may efficiently use coral sand where it is appropriate and minimize any constraints related to its qualities by taking these variables into consideration.

Acknowledgement

First of all, we want to give thanks to Almighty Allah. With his blessing we able to complete our work with best effort. We want to pay my utmost respect to my Supervisor Ms. Shi Ping, Assistant Professor of Department of Civil Engineering and Architecture, Shandong University of Technology for who has given me the chance to work on an impactful idea and taken care of every issue of development of this concept. Then we would like to take this opportunity to express gratitude to my supervisor for being dedicated in supporting, motivating and guiding us throughout this article. This article can't be done without her useful advice and help. Also thank her very much for giving me the opportunity to work with this thesis. Apart from that, we would like to thank to Hasan Md Mahmud fellows for sharing knowledge; information and helping us in making this article successful. To beloved families, we want to give them our deepest love and gratitude for being very supportive and also for their inspiration and encouragement.

References

Bolton, M., Nakata, Y., & Cheng, Y. (2008). Micro- and macro-mechanical behavior of DEM crushable material. *Geotechnique*, 58(6), 471–480. <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.2008.58.6.471>

Cavarretta, I., O'Sullivan, C., & Coop, M. (2017). The relevance of roundness to the crushing strength of granular materials. *Geotechnique*, 67(4), 301–312. <https://doi.org/10.1680/jgeot.15.P.226>

Chinese Ministry of Water Resources. (2019). Standard for soil test method (GB/T50123-2019) (in Chinese). China Planning Press, Beijing

Hong, Y., Koo, C., Zhou, C., Ng, C.W.W. & Wang, L. (2016). Small Strain Path-Dependent Stiffness of Toyoura Sand: Laboratory Measurement and Numerical Implementation. *International Journal of Geomechanics*, 17, 04016036. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GM.1943-5622.0000664](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GM.1943-5622.0000664)

Kolymbas, D. (1991). An outline of hypoplasticity. *Archive of Applied Mechanics*, 61, 143-151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00788048>

Lv, Y.R., Wang, Y., & Zuo, D.J. (2019) Effects of particle size on dynamic constitutive relation and energy absorption of calcareous sand. *Powder Technology*, 356, 21-30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2019.07.088>.

Lyu, B., Wang, A.G., Zhang, Z.H., Liu, K.W., Xu, H.Y., Shi, L. & Sun, D.S. (2019). Coral aggregate concrete: Numerical description of physical, chemical and morphological properties of coral aggregate. *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 100, 25-34. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2019.03.016>

Niemunis, A. & Herle, I. (1997). Hypoplastic Model for Cohesionless Soils with Elastic Strain Range. *Mechanics of Cohesive-frictional Materials*, 2, 279-299. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1484\(199710\)2:4<279::AID-CFM29>3.0.CO;2-8](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1484(199710)2:4<279::AID-CFM29>3.0.CO;2-8)

Peng, Y., Liu, H.L., Li, C., Ding, X.M., Deng, X. & Wang, C.Y. (2021). The detailed particle breakage around the pile in coral sand. *Acta Geotechnica*, 16(6), 1971–1981. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11440-020-01089-2>

Shen, J.H., Xu, D.S., Liu, Z.W. & Wei, H.Z. (2020). Effect of particle characteristics stress on the mechanical properties of cement mortar with coral sand. *Construction and Building Materials*, 260, 119836. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.11.9836>

von Wolffersdorff, P. (1996). A hypoplastic relation for granular materials with a predefined limit state surface. *Mechanics of Cohesive-frictional Materials*, 1, 251-271. [https://doi.org/10.1002/%28SICI%291099-1484%28199607%291%3A3%3C251%3A%3A%3A%3AID-CFM13%3E3.0.CO%3B2-3](https://doi.org/10.1002/%28SICI%291099-1484%28199607%291%3A3%3C251%3A%3A%3A%28199607%291%3A3%3C251%3A%3A%3A%3AID-CFM13%3E3.0.CO%3B2-3)

Wang, X., Cui, J., Zhu, C.Q., Wu, Y., & Wang, X.Z. (2021a) Experimental study of the mechanical behavior of calcareous sand under repeated loading-unloading. *Bull Eng Geol*

Environ, 80, 3097–3113.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10064-021-02119-3>.

Wang, X., Wang, X.Z., Zhu, C.Q. & Meng, Q.S. (2019b) Shear tests of interfaces between calcareous sand and steel. *Mar Georesources Geotechnol* 37:1095–1104.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1064119X.2018.1529845>

Wang, C., Ding, X., Cao, G., Jiang, C., Fang, H. & Wang, C. (2022) Numerical investigation of the effect of particle gradation on the lateral response of pile in coral sand. *Computers and Geotechnics*, 152, 105012.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11771-020-4557-x>

Wang, W., & Coop, M. (2016). An investigation of breakage behavior of single sand particles using a high-speed microscope camera. *Geotechnique*, 66(12), 984–998.
<https://doi.org/10.1680/jgeot.15.P.247>

Wang, X., Cui, J., Wu, Y., Zhu, C.Q. & Wang, X.Z. (2021). Mechanical properties of calcareous silts in a hydraulic fill island-reef. *Marine Georesources & Geotechnology*, 39(1), 1–14.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1064119X.2020.1748775>

Wang, X., Wu, Y., Cui, J., Zhu, C.Q. & Wang, X.Z. (2020). Shape characteristics of coral sand from the South China Sea. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 8(10), 803–827.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse8100803>

Wu, W. & Bauer, E. (1994). A simple hypoplastic constitutive model for sand. *International Journal for Numerical and Analytical Methods in Geomechanics*, 18, 833–862.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/nag.1610181203>

Wu, W. (1998). Hypoplasticity as a mathematical model for the mechanical behavior of granular materials.

Wu, W., & Kolymbas, D. (1990). Numerical testing of the stability criterion for hypoplastic constitutive equations. *Mechanics of Materials*, 9(3), 245–253.

Wu, W., Bauer, E., & Kolymbas, D. (1996). Hypoplastic constitutive model with critical state for granular materials. *Mechanics of Materials*, 23, 45–69.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-6636\(96\)00006-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-6636(96)00006-3)

Wu, Y., Li, N., Wang, X.Z., Cui, J., Chen, Y.L., Wu, Y.H. & Yamamoto, H. (2021). Experimental investigation on mechanical behavior and particle crushing of calcareous sand retrieved from South China Sea. *Engineering Geology*, 280, 105932.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enggeo.2020.105932>

Yu, X., Chen, L., Fang, Q., Zhang, J.H., Guo, D. & Hou, X.F. (2019). Determination of attenuation effects of coral sand on the propagation of impact-induced stress wave. *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, 125, 63–82.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijimpeng.2018.11.004>

Yuan-ying, L.I.U. (1994) Estimation of coastal aquifer permeability coefficient. *Groundwater* 02, 33–35.

Zhang, J.M., Wang, R., Shi, X.F., Li, J.G., & Chen, H.Y. (2005). Compression and crushing behavior of calcareous sand under confined compression (in Chinese). *Chinese Journal of Rock Mechanics and Engineering*, 24, 3327–3331.